

Modeling Lunar Surface Temperature

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Motivation/Objectives

Lunar surface temperature can provide insights into surface composition and volatile transport.

We sought to answer 2 questions:

1. How do different methods of modeling surface temperature compare to each other?
2. Is it possible to represent the results of thermal modeling using a mathematical expression?
 - Interpolating temperature profiles is important for simulations that require temperature as a parameter – an expression would be a lot less computationally complex than the model

Temperature Models

ReBL (Regolith Boundary Layer Model): solves one dimensional heat equation using thermophysical properties from [1], a Monte Carlo approach to compute radiative flux, and finite differencing to solve for temperature as function of depth and time [2].

Analytic Expression: set of equations from [3] that reproduces measured brightness temperatures.

Figure 1: Temperature at varying depths within 1 mm (thermal model) and brightness temperature (analytic function)

Interpolation

Figure 2: Temperature vs Latitude at various depths

Recursive Polynomial Regression

Using ReBL, **Temperature vs Latitude** at different depths is represented as a series of quadratic equations.

The **coefficients of these quadratic equations vs depth** can be represented by polynomials.

Solving these polynomials, with depth and latitude as inputs, we can find temperature at any given depth or latitude.

The brightness temperature is derived from the total radiation emitted from the near surface boundary layer (~1mm). Difference between brightness and model temperatures are the greatest at lunar noon, and smallest at night. Brightness temperature doesn't match any given depth temperature, which is important for applications where surface temperature is a variable, such as volatile transport.

Furthermore, the relationship between temperatures at various depths and the brightness temperature can help us understand the physical properties behind the depth temperatures.

Figure 3: ReBL temperature profiles compared to interpolated temperature profiles at different latitudes

Summary

Brightness and physical temperatures have differences which are significant in application and understanding thermophysical properties.

Temperature at different latitudes, depths, and times of day can be modeled as a computationally simple expression.

Future Investigations:

- Solve for brightness temperature with ReBL temperature profiles
- Create temperature database with interpolated profiles
- Validating the model and comparing to observation